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[Impact of Trust and Privacy on Repurchase Intention Through Customer Satisfaction Among Generation Z Instagram Shopper in Pakistan]

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ABSTRACT

Abstract: The rapid growth of social commerce has reshaped online consumer behaviour, particularly through interactive platforms such as Instagram. Generation Z represents a key segment whose trust and engagement influence platform success. This study aims to examine how platform trust indicators and institutional security assurance mechanisms affect cognitive trust, emotional trust, privacy concerns and subsequent outcomes including purchase intention, customer satisfaction and repurchase intention through the lens of Trust Transfer Theory and Security Assurance Theory. A quantitative, descriptive and correlational research design was adopted. Data were collected from 107 Generation Z Instagram users with prior purchasing experience using a structured questionnaire. The relationships among constructs were analyzed using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling. Social interactivity including responsiveness, user friendly content and peer engagement emerged as the strongest predictor of both cognitive and emotional trust. The findings support Security Assurance Theory by demonstrating that structured and predictable platform interactions enhance rational trust formation and enable trust transfer. However, perceived familiarity alone did not significantly influence trust, suggesting that exposure without interaction or assurance is insufficient. Institutional mechanisms such as privacy policies, assurance seals and third party certifications heightened privacy awareness, which influenced purchase intention. Cognitive trust was identified as the primary driver of purchase intention, which subsequently affected customer satisfaction and repurchase intention, while emotional trust played a supporting role. The study integrates Trust Transfer Theory and Security Assurance Theory to explain trust formation in social commerce and highlights the mediating role of privacy concerns. The findings provide practical insights for platform designers and marketers to enhance interactivity and transparently communicate security mechanisms to build trust, satisfaction and long term customer loyalty.

Keywords: *Cognitive Trust, Emotional Trust, Privacy Concerns, Purchase Intention, Customer Satisfaction, Repurchase Intention.*

Introduction

Commerce has historically been a socially embedded activity built on trust, reputation, and community norms. In traditional marketplaces, buyers reduced uncertainty through interpersonal familiarity and direct interaction with sellers. The emergence of the internet transformed these mechanisms by replacing face-to-face interaction with digital interfaces and requiring trust to be established through institutional safeguards such as secure payment systems, return policies, and customer feedback mechanisms (Gefen, 2000; McKnight et al., 2002). The rise of e-commerce in the late 1990s enhanced efficiency and convenience but simultaneously heightened concerns regarding privacy and risk. Consequently, institutional systems including

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encryption, privacy policies, and third-party certifications became essential in fostering consumer confidence (Pavlou, 2003; Pavlou & Gefen, 2004).

Social commerce represents the reintroduction of social dynamics into digital transactions. By integrating social media and e-commerce functionalities, social commerce enables consumers to discover, evaluate, and purchase products within interactive and socially engaged environments (Hajli, 2015). Unlike traditional e-commerce, which prioritizes transactional efficiency, social commerce emphasizes peer influence, community interaction, and relational trust. Platforms such as Instagram and TikTok function as hybrid marketplaces where product discovery intersects with identity expression and social engagement (Wu et al., 2023).

In Pakistan, social commerce has evolved in distinct ways. Instagram has emerged as a key marketplace for small businesses, entrepreneurs, and influencers who market products, interact with customers, and complete transactions via direct messaging and mobile payments. Unlike structured platforms such as Daraz, Instagram commerce largely operates informally without standardized policies or platform guarantees. Transactions are often grounded in perceived credibility and relational trust, making trust and privacy concerns particularly critical (Lakho & Rashid, 2025).

Generation Z, typically defined as individuals born between 1995 and 2015, represents a digitally native cohort whose consumption patterns are shaped by continuous connectivity and social media engagement. This generation values seamless digital experiences and interactive engagement while remaining highly conscious of privacy risks due to exposure to global debates on data misuse and surveillance (Szymkowiak et al., 2021). In Pakistan, where Generation Z constitutes a significant share of social media users, this dual orientation toward convenience and privacy awareness creates a unique context for examining trust in social commerce (Lakho & Rashid, 2025).

Trust is widely recognized as a central construct in online consumer behavior, particularly in environments characterized by uncertainty (Rousseau et al., 1998). In social commerce, trust is multidimensional, comprising cognitive trust based on rational assessments of reliability and competence, and emotional trust rooted in affective attachment and comfort (Fang et al., 2014; Singh, 2022). Empirical evidence consistently links trust to purchase and repurchase intentions as well as satisfaction outcomes.

Privacy concerns further complicate consumer decision-making in informal social commerce environments. Defined as perceived risks associated with data collection and misuse (Malhotra et al., 2004), privacy concerns can negatively influence purchase intention. However, institutional mechanisms such as privacy policies, assurance seals, and third-party certifications mitigate uncertainty and support trust formation (Pavlou & Gefen, 2004). This is particularly relevant in developing contexts like Pakistan, where regulatory protections remain limited.

Despite extensive research on trust and privacy in structured e-commerce settings, limited attention has been given to informal, relationship-driven environments such as Instagram commerce in developing economies. Moreover, Generation Z remains underexplored despite its central role in shaping digital consumption trends. Existing studies rarely examine how trust transfer mechanisms and institutional assurance signals

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influence not only purchase intention but also post-purchase outcomes such as satisfaction and repurchase intention.

Addressing this gap, the present study investigates how trust transfer factors including perceived familiarity, situational normality, platform trust, and social interactivity, together with institutional assurance mechanisms such as privacy policies, assurance seals, and third-party certifications, shape cognitive trust, emotional trust, and privacy concerns among Generation Z Instagram users in Pakistan. It further examines how these factors influence purchase intention, customer satisfaction, and repurchase intention within a unified framework grounded in Trust Transfer Theory, Security Assurance Theory, and post-purchase behavior perspectives.

This study contributes theoretically by integrating these frameworks to provide a holistic understanding of trust formation and behavioral outcomes in informal social commerce contexts. Practically, it offers insights for businesses and policymakers on strengthening consumer confidence through trust-building mechanisms and transparent privacy practices. Given the growing influence of Generation Z in Pakistan's digital economy, understanding these dynamics is essential for fostering sustainable social commerce ecosystems.

Literature Review

Theoretical Foundation

Trust Transfer Theory explains how consumers develop confidence in unfamiliar sellers within social commerce environments by transferring trust from a known platform to its associated actors (Stewart, 2003). In digital contexts such as Instagram, trust in the platform's reliability and security extends to individual sellers through cognitive and communicative processes (Liu et al., 2018; Wu et al., 2023), where antecedents such as perceived familiarity, situational normality, platform trust and social interactivity help build both cognitive trust based on rational evaluation and emotional trust rooted in affective comfort (Putri et al., 2024; Wiyata, 2023). Security Assurance Theory complements this by explaining how institutional safeguards such as privacy policies, assurance seals and third-party certifications reduce uncertainty and mitigate privacy concerns, thereby enhancing purchase intention in socially mediated environments (Ponte et al., 2015). Post-purchase behavior theories further extend this understanding by emphasizing the role of consumer evaluations in shaping satisfaction and repurchase intention, where Expectancy Disconfirmation Theory suggests satisfaction arises when performance meets expectations (Oliver, 1980), while Cognitive Dissonance Theory explains how unmet expectations generate psychological discomfort that influences loyalty (Feininger, 1957). Integrating these perspectives provides a comprehensive framework linking trust formation, privacy assurance and post-purchase outcomes to explain Generation Z consumer behavior in Instagram-based social commerce.

Repurchase Intention

Repurchase intention reflects a consumer's willingness to engage in repeat transactions with a platform or seller and is essential for sustaining long-term

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relationships. While purchase intention captures the initial decision to buy, repurchase intention represents continued confidence built through trust and satisfaction over time (Oliver, 1999). In social commerce, it is shaped by a combination of cognitive trust, emotional trust, privacy concerns and relational engagement, making it a multidimensional outcome rather than a purely transactional decision. Empirical research consistently highlights that trust and satisfaction jointly predict repurchase intention, with emotional trust becoming increasingly influential in long-term relationships (Fang et al., 2014; Singh, 2022). At the same time, privacy concerns play a complex role, as they can either weaken repurchase intention or be mitigated through trust depending on contextual factors (Trivedi & Yadav, 2020; Lu & Yi, 2023). For Generation Z, repurchase intention is influenced by both rational evaluations and emotional bonds with platforms and sellers (Szymkowiak et al., 2021). Studies indicate that social support and relational engagement strengthen trust and help sustain repeat purchasing even when privacy concerns are present (Tseng et al., 2025; Putri et al., 2024). In Pakistan, Instagram-based commerce reflects similar dynamics, where logical cues such as product information and platform reputation support initial confidence, while emotional trust and satisfaction sustain long-term engagement (Lakho & Rashid, 2025). Overall, repurchase intention emerges as a key outcome linking trust, satisfaction and privacy concerns, particularly in informal social commerce environments where institutional safeguards remain limited.

Customer Satisfaction

Customer satisfaction is widely recognized as a cornerstone of long-term consumer relationships and reflects the extent to which a consumer's expectations are met or exceeded during a transaction (Oliver, 1980). In social commerce, satisfaction extends beyond post-purchase evaluation to encompass trust, privacy concerns, social interaction and perceived relational value. Empirical research consistently shows that satisfaction plays a central role in predicting loyalty and repurchase behaviour, often acting as a bridge between trust and long-term engagement (Fang et al., 2014). Studies further demonstrate that cognitive trust mediates the relationship between privacy assurance mechanisms and satisfaction, while emotional attachment enhances consumer evaluations in digitally mediated environments (Punyatoya, 2019; Singh, 2022; Wu et al., 2023). Among Generation Z, satisfaction is shaped by both rational and affective experiences. This cohort values seamless digital interactions alongside emotional engagement, making satisfaction dependent on both platform reliability and relational bonds (Szymkowiak et al., 2021; Tseng et al., 2025). Research also indicates that emotional trust can mitigate privacy concerns and sustain satisfaction in social commerce settings (Putri et al., 2024). In Pakistan, particularly within Instagram-based commerce, satisfaction emerges from the interplay of trust, privacy perceptions and social interaction (Lakho & Rashid, 2025). While informational cues such as product details and platform reputation contribute to satisfaction, emotional trust plays a vital role in sustaining engagement despite privacy risks. Overall, satisfaction serves as a critical link connecting trust, privacy concerns and long-term consumer loyalty in informal social

commerce environments.

Purchase Intension

Purchase intention is widely regarded as a key predictor of actual buying behavior and represents a consumer's willingness to engage in transactions within social commerce environments such as Instagram (Ajzen, 1991). In this context, purchase intention is shaped by multiple factors including trust, privacy concerns, social interaction and perceived value. Empirical research consistently highlights its central role in linking psychological antecedents to consumer actions. Studies show that cognitive trust, driven by platform reliability and information quality, significantly influences purchase intention, while emotional trust enhances consumer engagement and confidence (Wu et al., 2023; Fang et al., 2014). Among Generation Z, purchase intention reflects both rational evaluation and emotional attachment, as this cohort values platform credibility alongside interactive and relational experiences (Szymkowiak et al., 2021). Research further indicates that trust can mitigate the negative effects of privacy concerns, enabling consumers to engage in social commerce despite perceived risks (Tseng et al., 2025; Putri et al., 2024). In Pakistan, Instagram-based commerce demonstrates similar dynamics, where Gen Z consumers rely on product information and platform reputation to form purchase intentions, while emotional trust in relational bonds sustains engagement (Lakho & Rashid, 2025). Overall, purchase intention emerges as a critical outcome of trust and privacy perceptions, highlighting the importance of fostering both cognitive and emotional trust to support consumer participation in informal social commerce environments.

Privacy Concern

Privacy concerns have emerged as a critical issue in social commerce, particularly in environments where platforms collect and process personal data without strong regulatory safeguards. Unlike traditional e-commerce, social commerce often operates in informal settings, making privacy risks more pronounced. For Generation Z consumers, who are highly active on social media yet increasingly aware of data security threats, privacy concerns significantly influence trust, purchase intention and repurchase behaviour. Foundational studies in e-commerce highlight the role of institutional safeguards such as privacy policies and third-party certifications in reducing perceived risk and enhancing trust (Pavlou, 2003; Malhotra et al., 2004). Empirical research in social commerce contexts confirms that privacy concerns negatively impact purchase intention, although trust can mitigate this effect (Punyatoya, 2019; Tseng et al., 2025). Studies further indicate that privacy concerns may either moderate or be mediated by trust, influencing consumer confidence even when platforms are perceived as reliable (Lu & Yi, 2023; Trivedi & Yadav, 2020). Among Generation Z, privacy sensitivity coexists with a preference for seamless digital engagement, making trust essential for overcoming perceived risks (Szymkowiak et al., 2021; Putri et al., 2024). In Pakistan's Instagram-based commerce, where regulatory protection remains limited, privacy concerns play a decisive

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role in shaping consumer behaviour (Lakho & Rashid, 2025). While cognitive trust in platform reputation helps alleviate perceived risks, emotional trust in relational bonds sustains engagement despite uncertainty. Overall, privacy concerns remain a central determinant influencing trust formation, purchase decisions and long-term participation in informal social commerce environments.

Emotional Trust

Emotional trust refers to confidence grounded in affective responses rather than purely rational evaluation, reflecting the extent to which consumers feel safe, valued and emotionally connected to a seller (Johnson & Grayson, 2005). Unlike cognitive trust, which is based on perceptions of competence and reliability, emotional trust develops through relational warmth, empathy and social interaction (McKnight et al., 2002). In social commerce environments, particularly those that are informal and socially integrated, emotional trust emerges through personalized communication, social presence and interactive engagement (Hajli, 2015). Empirical studies highlight its growing importance in shaping long-term consumer outcomes such as satisfaction, loyalty and repurchase intention (Fang et al., 2014; Hanabir, 2023). Research suggests that while cognitive trust drives initial purchase decisions, emotional trust becomes increasingly influential in sustaining ongoing relationships (Singh, 2022). Among Generation Z, emotional engagement plays a central role in shaping digital interactions, as this cohort values authenticity and relational connection alongside informational cues (Szymkowiak et al., 2021). In visually driven platforms such as Instagram, features like influencer engagement, live interactions and peer feedback foster emotional attachment that enhances purchase intention and loyalty (Putri et al., 2024; Tseng et al., 2025). In Pakistan's Instagram-based commerce, emotional trust is particularly significant due to limited formal safeguards. Gen Z consumers often rely on relational bonds formed through social interaction to compensate for perceived risks (Lakho & Rashid, 2025). Overall, emotional trust serves as a critical mechanism that supports engagement and long-term participation in social commerce despite privacy uncertainties.

Cognitive Trust

Cognitive trust represents the rational dimension of trust, grounded in evidence-based evaluations of a seller's reliability, competence and integrity (McKnight et al., 2002). In social commerce, it develops through observable cues such as platform reputation, information quality, transaction transparency and security assurances (Oliveira et al., 2017; Senali et al., 2024). Integrating trust into the Technology Acceptance Model, Karahanna and Straub (2003) demonstrated that cognitive trust significantly influences purchase intention in online contexts. In environments where formal protections are limited, system-based mechanisms such as privacy policies and third-party certifications help signal reliability and reduce perceived risk (Pavlou, 2003). Empirical research consistently identifies cognitive trust as a strong predictor of purchase intention and a mediator between platform cues and consumer behaviour (Wang et al., 2022; Wu et al., 2023). Among Generation Z, cognitive trust is shaped by expectations of seamless, secure digital experiences and is influenced by platform credibility and

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information quality (Szymkowiak et al., 2021; Tseng et al., 2025). In Pakistan's largely informal Instagram-based commerce, cognitive trust becomes particularly important as consumers rely on logical cues such as product information and platform authenticity to compensate for weak regulatory safeguards (Lakho & Rashid, 2025). Overall, cognitive trust provides the foundational confidence necessary for initial engagement in social commerce by reducing uncertainty and supporting purchase decisions.

Emotional Trust

Emotional trust has gained increasing attention in recent social commerce literature as a key affective mechanism shaping consumer behavior. Unlike cognitive trust, which is based on rational evaluations of competence and reliability, emotional trust reflects feelings of security, care and relational attachment toward a seller or platform (Johnson & Grayson, 2005). In socially interactive environments, emotional trust develops through communication, perceived empathy and social presence, making it particularly relevant in informal digital marketplaces (Hajli, 2015). Recent studies highlight that emotional trust significantly enhances consumer engagement and willingness to transact in social commerce settings (Hanabir, 2023; Wu et al., 2023). Empirical research demonstrates that emotional trust strengthens purchase intention and loyalty by fostering deeper relational bonds between consumers and sellers (Putri et al., 2024). Among Generation Z, emotional engagement plays an especially important role, as this cohort values authenticity and personalized interaction alongside functional platform performance (Szymkowiak et al., 2021). Studies further indicate that emotional trust mediates the relationship between social support and purchase intention, reinforcing consumer confidence in digitally mediated environments (Tseng et al., 2025). In addition, emotional trust has been found to offset perceived risks and privacy concerns, thereby sustaining long-term participation in social commerce platforms (Singh, 2022).

Hypothesis Development

Trust is a cornerstone of social commerce, and in Instagram commerce among Generation Z in Pakistan, it is shaped by specific antecedents: perceived familiarity, situational normality, trust in platform, and social interactivity. Each of these antecedents provides unique signals that help consumers reduce uncertainty and form confidence in sellers. In a context where system based security is weak, these antecedents become even more critical in shaping both cognitive trust (rational evaluation of competence and reliability) and emotional trust (affective bonds and relational closeness).

Perceived familiarity defined as that in which consumers feel they know the seller or the platform through different exposure, repeated interactions, or recognition. Familiarity reduces uncertainty and build confidence in transactions. Gefen (2000) emphasized that familiarity is a key antecedent of trust in online environments. In Instagram commerce, perceived familiarity is expected to influence both cognitive and emotional trust in sellers.

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H1a: *Perceived familiarity influences cognitive trust in sellers.*

H1b: *Perceived familiarity influences emotional trust in sellers.*

Situational normality refers to the perception that transactions occur in a predictable and orderly environment. When consumers feel that Instagram commerce follows expected norms and routines, they are more likely to trust sellers. Stewart (2003) confirmed that situational normality is a critical antecedent of trust formation. In Pakistan's Instagram commerce, situational normality is expected to influence both cognitive and emotional trust.

H2a: *Situational normality influences cognitive trust in sellers.*

H2b: *Situational normality influences emotional trust in sellers.*

Trust in the platform reflects the belief that Instagram itself provides a safe, reliable, and valid environment for commerce. When consumers perceive the platform as credible and protective, they are more likely to extend trust to sellers operating within it. Pavlou & Gefen (2004) highlighted that platform trust enhances consumer confidence in online transactions. In Instagram commerce, trust in the platform is expected to influence both cognitive and emotional trust in sellers.

H3a: *Trust in platform influences cognitive trust in sellers.*

H3b: *Trust in platform influences emotional trust in sellers.*

Social interactivity captures the role of engagement, comments, peer activity, and influencer endorsements in shaping perceptions of trust. In Instagram commerce, social interactivity builds relational bonds and creates a sense of community, which is particularly important for Generation Z consumers in Pakistan. Hajli (2015) emphasized that social interaction enhances both cognitive and emotional trust by providing social proof and relational closeness.

H4a: *Social interactivity influences cognitive trust in sellers.*

H4b: *Social interactivity influences emotional trust in sellers.*

Cognitive trust is grounded in rational assessments of competence and reliability, while emotional trust is based on affective bonds and relational closeness. Gefen (2000) and Fang et al. (2014) found that cognitive trust exerts stronger effects on purchase intention than emotional trust. Yet emotional trust, cultivated through social presence and relational engagement, also plays a role in shaping consumer decisions. In Pakistan's Instagram commerce, both dimensions are expected to influence purchase intention.

H5a: *Cognitive trust in seller's influences intention to purchase or use.*

H5b: *Emotional trust in seller's influences intention to purchase or use.*

Trust has also been linked to satisfaction in related studies. Fang et al. (2014) and Punyatoya (2019) investigate that trust dimensions significantly influence satisfaction. In Instagram commerce, cognitive trust is expected to enhance satisfaction by assuring consumers of the seller's competence and reliability, while emotional trust is expected to enhance satisfaction by building a sense of comfort and relational closeness.

H6a: *Cognitive trust in seller's influences customer satisfaction.*

H6b: *Emotional trust in seller's influences customer satisfaction.*

Privacy concerns are particularly important in Pakistan, where organizational enforcement of privacy regulations is limited. Generation Z consumers, despite being

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digitally fluent, are highly aware of risks such as fraud and data misuse. System based security such as assurance seals, transparency in data handling, and privacy and security policies are expected to play a key role in shaping privacy concerns. Belanger et al. (2002) and Pavlou & Gefen (2004) demonstrated that assurance seals, privacy policies, and transparency suggestions reduce consumer privacy concerns. In Instagram commerce, these signals are expected to control privacy concerns among Pakistani Generation Z consumers.

H7a: Assurance seals influence consumers' privacy concerns in Instagram commerce.

H7b: Data transparency influences consumers' privacy concerns in Instagram commerce.

H7c: Privacy and security policies influence consumers' privacy concerns in Instagram commerce.

Privacy concerns themselves have consistently been found to reduce consumer willingness to transact online. Malhotra et al. (2004) and Kimery & McCord (2002) confirmed that privacy concerns shape consumer decision-making. In Instagram commerce, where transactions often involve personal data and informal sellers, privacy concerns are expected to influence purchase intention.

H8: Privacy concerns influence intention to purchase or use Instagram commerce.

Purchase intention is not only a rational decision but also a reflection of social influence and peer validation. Oliver (1980) argued that favourable intentions lead to positive consumption experiences, which in turn build satisfaction. In Instagram commerce, when consumers decide to purchase based on trust and reduced privacy concerns, they are more likely to report satisfaction with their experience.

H9: Intention to purchase or use influences customer satisfaction in Instagram commerce.

Customer satisfaction is not only the result of a single transaction but also forecasts the future purchase. Oliver (1999) emphasized that satisfaction is a critical antecedent of loyalty and repurchase intention. Trivedi and Yadav (2020) further confirmed that satisfaction plays a key role in sustaining consumer engagement in digital marketplaces. In Pakistan's Instagram commerce, satisfaction is expected to encourage repeat purchases among Generation Z consumers.

H10: Customer satisfaction influences repurchase intention in Instagram commerce.

Figure: 1

Methodology

This study adopts a quantitative, survey-based research design grounded in a deductive approach to test hypotheses derived from Trust Transfer Theory, Security Assurance Theory and Post-Purchase Behaviour Theory (Creswell, 2014). A cross-sectional design was employed to capture consumer attitudes and behaviours at a single point in time, which is consistent with established practices in consumer behaviour research (Bryman & Bell, 2015). Guided by a positivist research philosophy, the study assumes that reality is objective and measurable through observable phenomena, making it appropriate for examining relationships among constructs such as trust, privacy concerns and behavioural intentions. A survey strategy was implemented using a structured questionnaire to facilitate standardized data collection and statistical analysis, with the target population comprising Generation Z Instagram users in Pakistan, defined as individuals born between 1995 and 2015 due to their high engagement in social commerce activities (Szymkowiak et al., 2021). A purposive non-probability sampling technique was used to ensure respondents were active Instagram users with prior online purchasing experience (Etikan et al., 2016). From an initial 300 responses, 107 valid responses were retained after screening, meeting the adequacy requirement for PLS-SEM analysis based on the 10-times rule (Hair et al., 2017). Data were collected through both online platforms such as WhatsApp, Instagram and Facebook, and offline distribution in universities across Karachi to enhance diversity and reduce sampling bias. Measurement scales were adapted from validated studies and assessed using a five-point Likert scale (Joshi et al., 2015). Data were analyzed using Partial Least Squares Structural

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Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) via SmartPLS, suitable for complex models and smaller samples (Hair et al., 2019). Reliability and validity were ensured through Cronbach’s alpha, composite reliability and AVE, while ethical standards were maintained through voluntary participation and confidentiality. Although limitations such as purposive sampling, self-reported data and cross-sectional design exist, the methodology remains aligned with established social commerce research practices (Putri et al., 2024; Wu et al., 2023).

Data Analysis and Results

Sample Characteristics

The study surveyed 107 Generation Z respondents aged 18–26, all active Instagram users, with a balanced gender distribution of 46.7% males and 53.3% females. Most participants were undergraduates (65.4%) and students (70.1%), reflecting typical young social media users (Pew Research Center, 2021; Smith & Anderson, 2018). Daily Instagram usage varied, with the majority spending 2–4 hours on the platform, engaging mainly in browsing, following brands, messaging and content sharing. In terms of purchase behaviour, 87.9% had previously made purchases via Instagram, with over half reporting occasional transactions. Among these, 87.2% expressed a strong intention to repurchase from the same sellers. Overall, the sample reflects a representative profile of Gen Z Instagram users with relevant purchasing experience.

Table-1

Sample Characteristics

Variable		frequency	%
Age	18–20	35	32.7
	21–23	42	39.3
	24–26	30	28.0
Gender	Male	50	46.7
	Female	57	53.3
Education	High School / Diploma	15	14.0
	Undergraduate	70	65.4
	Postgraduate	22	20.6
Occupation	Student	75	70.1
	Employed	25	23.4
	Self-employed / Freelancer	7	6.5
Instagram Usage (daily)	<1 hour	10	9.3
	1–2 hours	32	29.9
	2–4 hours	40	37.4
	>4 hours	25	23.4
Instagram Activities	Posting content	28	26.2

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	Browsing stories / feed	79	73.8
	Messaging / DMs	55	51.4
	Following brands / influencers	70	65.4
Instagram Purchase Experience	Yes	94	87.9
	No	13	12.1
Purchase Frequency (last 6 months)	Occasional (1–2 times)	48	51.1
	Regular (3–5 times)	32	34.0
	Frequent (>5 times)	14	14.9
Repurchase Intention	Likely to repurchase	82	87.2
	Unlikely	12	12.8

N = 107

Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics were computed at the construct level by averaging item responses to represent latent variables, as recommended in PLS-SEM analysis (Hair et al., 2017). Results indicate moderate perceptions across key constructs. Perceived Familiarity and Situational Normality showed mean scores of 2.82 and 2.95 respectively, reflecting moderate platform familiarity and perceived normality of interactions. Trust in Platform (M = 3.10) and Social Interactivity (M = 2.97) indicated slightly positive evaluations of platform reliability and engagement features. Cognitive Trust (M = 3.01) and Emotional Trust (M = 3.00) demonstrated balanced trust perceptions. Privacy-related constructs also showed moderate levels, with Privacy Control (M = 3.06) and Disposition to Third Party Certification (M = 2.96). Customer Satisfaction (M = 3.15) and Repurchase Intention (M = 3.10) reflected generally favorable outcomes. Skewness and kurtosis values remained within acceptable limits (± 2), supporting approximate normality for SEM analysis (Kline, 2015).

Table-2

Descriptive Statistics

Construct	Mean	SD	Skewness	Kurtosis
Perceived Familiarity (PF)	2.82	1.31	0.088	-0.997
Situational Normality (SN)	2.95	1.25	-0.129	-0.928
Trust in Platform (TP)	3.10	1.28	-0.233	-0.979
Social Interactivity (SI)	2.97	1.23	-0.123	-0.900

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Cognitive Trust (CT)	3.01	1.25	-0.207	-0.929
Emotional Trust (ET)	3.00	1.26	-0.104	-0.902
Privacy Control (PC)	3.06	1.27	-0.177	-0.962
Disposition to Third Party (DT)	2.96	1.26	-0.087	-0.936
Customer Satisfaction (CS)	3.15	1.26	-0.356	-0.818
Repurchase Intention (RP)	3.10	1.28	-0.252	-0.916

Measurement Model

To evaluate the measurement model, the factor loadings, construct reliability and the construct validity were evaluated. The study constructs have been theoretically conceptualized to be multidimensional; however, empirical analysis of the study showed that intercorrelations among the dimensions are high thus indicating high overlap. In line with the measurement theory, indicators that are strongly loaded, have adequate reliability and convergent validity may be considered empirically unidimensional (Churchill, 1979; Anderson and Gerbing, 1988). According to the previous guidelines in PLS- SEM, the parsimonious unidimensional specification should be used when the lower-order constructs fail to provide sufficient discriminant validity and measure the same conceptual domain (Hair et al., 2017; Hair et al., 2021). Additionally, high levels of HTMT supported the existence of one underlying construct as opposed to different dimensions (Henseler et al., 2015). In this regard, any indicator was modeled as reflective measurements of the one latent construct in the final analysis.

Figure: 2

To determine the indicator reliability and convergent validity, the measurement model was tested through inspection of indicators loading. Each of them had strong standardized loadings, with the range of 0.862 to 0.980, which is more than the recommended level of 0.70, which confirms satisfactory indicators of reliability (Hair et al., 2017; Hair et al., 2021). The very high loadings of all constructs are indicative of adequate convergent validity (Anderson & Gerbing, 1988). Following the measurement theory, reflective indicators that have a high degree of empirical overlap were included in the parsimonious unidimensional specifications to prevent redundancy and guarantee model validity (Churchill, 1979; Jarvis et al., 2003; Henseler et al., 2015).

Reliability and Validity Measures

Before assessing structural relationships, internal consistency reliability was evaluated to ensure that all measurement instruments accurately captured their intended latent constructs. Cronbach’s alpha was used as an initial reliability measure, as it is widely accepted in social science research for assessing scale consistency (Nunnally & Bernstein, 1994; Hair et al., 2019). Indicator reliability was further examined through standardized outer loadings, where a threshold of 0.708 or higher is recommended to confirm that constructs explain at least 50% of the variance in their indicators (Hair et al.,

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2019). The results showed strong indicator reliability, with loadings ranging from 0.714 to 0.897. Most indicators exceeded the recommended threshold, with several above 0.80, indicating strong measurement quality. As no indicator fell below 0.70, all items were retained, confirming that each contributed meaningfully to its respective construct and that the measurement model met reliability requirements.

Table-4
Reliability Analysis

	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability
AS	0.819	0.881
CS	0.741	0.885
CT	0.873	0.908
DT	0.830	0.887
ET	0.797	0.881
PC	0.868	0.902
PF	0.819	0.881
PI	0.921	0.937
PS	0.802	0.871
RP	0.804	0.885
SI	0.917	0.935
SN	0.866	0.903
TP	0.889	0.919

The reliability analysis demonstrates strong internal consistency across all constructs in the study. Cronbach's alpha values range from 0.741 to 0.921, exceeding the recommended threshold of 0.70, which confirms that all constructs exhibit satisfactory reliability. Similarly, composite reliability values fall between 0.871 and 0.937, further supporting the robustness of the measurement model, as values above 0.70 indicate adequate internal consistency (Hair et al., 2019). Among the constructs, Purchase Intention (PI) and Social Interactivity (SI) show the highest reliability, with Cronbach's alpha values of 0.921 and 0.917 respectively, alongside strong composite reliability scores (0.937 and 0.935). Cognitive Trust (CT), Trust in Platform (TP), Privacy Concerns (PC) and Situational Normality (SN) also demonstrate high reliability, with both Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability values comfortably above recommended levels. Constructs such as Customer Satisfaction (CS) and Emotional Trust (ET), although comparatively lower, still exceed acceptable thresholds, confirming their measurement stability.

Convergent validity

Convergent validity was assessed using the Average Variance Extracted (AVE), which represents the average proportion of variance that a construct explains in its

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indicators. An AVE value of 0.50 or higher indicates adequate convergent validity (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). The AVE values for all constructs exceeded the recommended threshold, ranging from **0.606 to 0.794**. These results indicate that each construct explains more than half of the variance in its indicators on average, confirming that the indicators converge well in measuring their respective latent constructs. Consequently, convergent validity is established for all constructs in the measurement model.

Table-5

Average variance extracted (AVE)

	Average variance extracted (AVE)
AS	0.649
CS	0.794
CT	0.665
DT	0.663
ET	0.712
PC	0.606
PF	0.651
PI	0.680
PS	0.627
RP	0.720
SI	0.707
SN	0.651
TP	0.693

Discriminant validity

The evaluation of discriminant validity was performed using Fornell Larcker criterion and the heterotrait -Monotrait (HTMT) ratio. The Fornell-Larcker test showed that the square root of the average variance extracted (AVE) of each of the constructs were larger than the inter construct-relations and therefore supported construct distinctiveness (Fornell and Larcker, 1981). Further, the full range of HTMT ratios were less than the recommended cut-offs (0.85/0.90) and therefore, offered formidable evidence of discriminant validity in the measurement model (Henseler et al., 2015).

Table – 6

Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT) Ratios for Discriminant Validity

	AS	CS	CT	DT	ET	PC	PF	PI	PS	RP	SI	SN	TP
AS													
CS	0.787												
CT	0.873	0.894											

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DT	0.870	0.839	0.862										
ET	0.804	0.880	0.880	0.785									
PC	0.895	0.872	0.854	0.880	0.811								
PF	0.776	0.597	0.752	0.848	0.688	0.777							
PI	0.827	0.850	0.860	0.849	0.881	0.840	0.750						
PS	0.819	0.807	0.889	0.710	0.860	0.870	0.718	0.843					
RP	0.691	0.880	0.867	0.733	0.878	0.825	0.642	0.812	0.797				
SI	0.755	0.721	0.850	0.711	0.840	0.778	0.707	0.793	0.884	0.737			
SN	0.792	0.663	0.868	0.763	0.762	0.822	0.866	0.804	0.832	0.657	0.754		
TP	0.841	0.723	0.890	0.860	0.825	0.889	0.850	0.872	0.840	0.743	0.805	0.880	

In the Table 6, Fornell-Larcker assessment, the square root of the average variance extracted by all the constructs is larger than the inter-construct correlations, thus supporting discriminant validity (Fornell and Larcker, 1981).

Table – 7
Fornell Larcker Criterion

	AS	CS	CT	DT	ET	PC	PF	PI	PS	RP	SI	SN	TP
AS	0.806												
CS	0.609	0.891											
CT	0.734	0.720	0.815										
DT	0.778	0.657	0.733	0.814									
ET	0.647	0.675	0.812	0.639	0.844								
PC	0.756	0.700	0.745	0.765	0.675	0.778							
PF	0.637	0.467	0.643	0.696	0.559	0.655	0.807						
PI	0.714	0.770	0.833	0.742	0.755	0.810	0.649	0.825					
PS	0.661	0.624	0.748	0.579	0.745	0.728	0.585	0.727	0.792				
RP	0.560	0.697	0.728	0.602	0.706	0.688	0.520	0.698	0.640	0.848			
SI	0.653	0.594	0.816	0.617	0.776	0.692	0.611	0.726	0.756	0.633	0.841		
SN	0.661	0.534	0.760	0.646	0.636	0.714	0.734	0.723	0.699	0.550	0.673	0.807	
TP	0.714	0.590	0.787	0.786	0.697	0.780	0.786	0.790	0.708	0.629	0.727	0.838	0.833

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Structural Equation Modeling

To test the hypothesized interrelations of constructs, Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) based on SmartPLS was used to concurrently test the relationship among these constructs. SEM allowed measuring both the measurement and the structural aspects, and as a result, provided an opportunity to estimate the path coefficients, significance rates, and explanatory power, thus providing a rigorous evaluation of the effect of direct, mediating, and moderating in the proposed research model.

Table – 8
Direct Effect (Path Coefficients)

	β	SD	t-values	p-values
PF → CT	-0.035	0.077	0.453	0.650
PF → ET	-0.043	0.109	0.389	0.697
SN → CT	0.243	0.092	2.634	0.008
SN → ET	0.064	0.121	0.526	0.599
TP → CT	0.256	0.174	1.470	0.142
TP → ET	0.266	0.135	1.967	0.049
SI → CT	0.487	0.101	4.836	<0.001
SI → ET	0.566	0.120	4.733	<0.001
CT → PI	0.414	0.108	3.815	<0.001
ET → PI	0.148	0.089	1.658	0.097
PI → CS	0.770	0.067	11.531	<0.001
CS → RP	0.697	0.069	10.151	<0.001
AS → PC	0.217	0.109	1.980	0.048
DT → PC	0.388	0.096	4.055	<0.001
PS → PC	0.360	0.087	4.158	<0.001
PC → PI	0.402	0.070	5.768	<0.001

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The structural model results provide important insights into the relationships among trust antecedents, privacy mechanisms and behavioural outcomes. Perceived Familiarity (PF) did not significantly influence either Cognitive Trust (CT) ($\beta = -0.035$, $p = 0.650$) or Emotional Trust (ET) ($\beta = -0.043$, $p = 0.697$), indicating that mere familiarity with the platform does not contribute to trust formation. Situational Normality (SN) significantly influenced Cognitive Trust ($\beta = 0.243$, $p = 0.008$), suggesting that when platform interactions are perceived as typical and expected, users are more likely to develop rational trust, although its effect on Emotional Trust was not significant ($p = 0.599$). Trust in Platform (TP) significantly influenced Emotional Trust ($\beta = 0.266$, $p = 0.049$) but not Cognitive Trust, indicating that platform reliability contributes more to affective confidence than rational evaluation.

Social Interactivity (SI) emerged as the strongest predictor of both Cognitive Trust ($\beta = 0.487$, $p < 0.001$) and Emotional Trust ($\beta = 0.566$, $p < 0.001$), highlighting the importance of interactive engagement in building trust. Cognitive Trust significantly influenced Purchase Intention (PI) ($\beta = 0.414$, $p < 0.001$), while Emotional Trust showed no significant effect, suggesting that rational trust drives initial transactions. Purchase Intention strongly influenced Customer Satisfaction (CS) ($\beta = 0.770$, $p < 0.001$), which in turn significantly predicted Repurchase Intention (RP) ($\beta = 0.697$, $p < 0.001$).

Regarding privacy mechanisms, Assurance Seals (AS), Disposition to Third-party Certification (DT) and Privacy/Security Policy (PS) all significantly influenced Privacy Concerns (PC). Finally, Privacy Concerns positively influenced Purchase Intention ($\beta = 0.402$, $p < 0.001$), indicating that awareness of privacy protections enhances transactional confidence. Overall, the findings highlight the dominant role of social interactivity, cognitive trust and institutional assurance in shaping consumer behaviour

Table – 9
Indirect Effect

	β	SD	t-Values	p-values
PS → PC → PI	0.145	0.045	3.222	0.001
DT → PC → PI	0.156	0.053	2.964	0.003
AS → PC → PI	0.087	0.045	1.920	0.055
PI → CS → RP	0.537	0.081	6.637	<0.001
CT → PI → CS	0.319	0.084	3.804	<0.001
ET → PI → CS	0.030	0.028	1.095	0.274

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The mediation analysis provides further insight into the indirect relationships among institutional mechanisms, trust outcomes and behavioural intentions. The results indicate that Privacy/Security Policy (PS) and Disposition to Third-party Certification (DT) significantly influence Purchase Intention (PI) through Privacy Concerns (PC), with indirect effects of $\beta = 0.145$ ($p = 0.001$) and $\beta = 0.156$ ($p = 0.003$) respectively. This suggests that institutional safeguards enhance purchase intention by shaping consumers' perceptions of privacy protection. However, the indirect effect of Assurance Seals (AS) on Purchase Intention through Privacy Concerns was not statistically significant ($\beta = 0.087$, $p = 0.055$), indicating a weaker mediating role.

Furthermore, Purchase Intention significantly influenced Repurchase Intention (RP) through Customer Satisfaction (CS) ($\beta = 0.537$, $p < 0.001$), highlighting the critical role of satisfaction in translating initial purchase decisions into long-term loyalty. Similarly, Cognitive Trust (CT) had a significant indirect effect on Customer Satisfaction via Purchase Intention ($\beta = 0.319$, $p < 0.001$), demonstrating that rational trust enhances satisfaction through increased willingness to transact. In contrast, Emotional Trust (ET) did not show a significant indirect effect ($\beta = 0.030$, $p = 0.274$), suggesting its limited role in shaping satisfaction through purchase intention. Overall, the findings emphasize the importance of privacy assurance and cognitive trust in driving behavioural outcomes.

Table – 12
Hypothesis Summary

Hypothesis	Path	β	t-values	p-values	Supported?
H1a	PF → CT	-0.035	0.453	0.650	Not Supported
H1b	PF → ET	-0.043	0.389	0.697	Not Supported
H2a	SN → CT	0.243	2.634	0.008	Supported
H2b	SN → ET	0.064	0.526	0.599	Not Supported
H3a	TP → CT	0.256	1.470	0.142	Not Supported
H3b	TP → ET	0.266	1.967	0.049	Supported
H4a	SI → CT	0.487	4.836	0.000	Supported
H4b	SI → ET	0.566	4.733	0.000	Supported
H5a	CT → PI	0.414	3.815	0.000	Supported

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H5b	ET → PI	0.148	1.658	0.097	Not Supported
H6a	CT → CS	0.770	11.531	0.000	Supported (via PI)
H6b	ET → CS	0.030	1.095	0.274	Not Supported
H7a	PS → PC	0.360	4.158	0.000	Supported
H7b	DT → PC	0.388	4.055	0.000	Supported
H7c	AS → PC	0.217	1.980	0.048	Supported
H8	PC → PI	0.402	5.768	0.000	Supported
H9	PI → CS	0.770	11.531	0.000	Supported
H10	CS → RP	0.697	10.151	0.000	Supported
H11	Institutional → PC → PI	PS: 0.145, DT:0.156, AS:0.087	PS:3.222, DT:2.964, AS:1.920	PS:0.001, DT:0.003, AS:0.055	Supported
H12	PI → CS → RP	0.537	6.637	0.000	Supported

The hypothesis testing results provide clear insights into the relationships within the proposed model. Hypotheses H1a and H1b, examining the effect of Perceived Familiarity on Cognitive Trust and Emotional Trust, were not supported, indicating that familiarity alone does not significantly contribute to trust formation. Situational Normality significantly influenced Cognitive Trust (H2a supported), but not Emotional Trust (H2b not supported). Trust in Platform showed a significant impact only on Emotional Trust (H3b supported), suggesting its stronger affective influence rather than rational impact.

Social Interactivity emerged as a key determinant, significantly influencing both Cognitive Trust and Emotional Trust (H4a and H4b supported). Cognitive Trust significantly predicted Purchase Intention (H5a supported), whereas Emotional Trust did not (H5b not supported). Cognitive Trust also indirectly influenced Customer Satisfaction via Purchase Intention (H6a supported), while Emotional Trust did not (H6b not supported).

Institutional mechanisms, including Privacy/Security Policy, Disposition to Third-party Certification, and Assurance Seals, significantly influenced Privacy Concerns (H7a, H7b, H7c supported), which in turn significantly affected Purchase Intention (H8 supported). Purchase Intention strongly predicted Customer Satisfaction (H9 supported), and Customer Satisfaction significantly influenced Repurchase Intention (H10 supported).

Mediation analysis confirmed that institutional mechanisms influence Purchase

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Intention through Privacy Concerns (H11 supported), and that Purchase Intention influences Repurchase Intention through Customer Satisfaction (H12 supported). Overall, the findings highlight the dominant role of social interactivity, cognitive trust, and institutional assurance in shaping consumer behaviour.

Discussion and Conclusion

The study examined how platform trust cues including perceived familiarity, situational normality, social interactivity and trust in platform, along with institutional assurance mechanisms such as privacy security policy, assurance seals and disposition to third-party certification, influence trust formation, privacy concerns and behavioural outcomes including purchase intention, customer satisfaction and repurchase intention.

Among the platform trust cues, perceived familiarity did not significantly influence either cognitive or emotional trust. This suggests that passive exposure to a platform is insufficient for trust formation among digitally sophisticated Gen Z users who interact with multiple platforms regularly. Instead, trust appears to be driven by observable and experiential cues rather than familiarity alone, aligning with emerging research that highlights the declining importance of familiarity as a heuristic in highly digitalised environments.

Situational normality significantly influenced cognitive trust but not emotional trust, indicating that predictable and orderly platform environments foster rational confidence in reliability without necessarily generating emotional attachment. This distinction reinforces the idea that cognitive and emotional trust develop through different mechanisms.

Social interactivity emerged as the most influential platform cue, significantly shaping both cognitive and emotional trust. Interactive features such as responsiveness, user engagement and social presence were found to enhance both logical confidence and affective comfort. This highlights the central role of social interaction in trust formation within social commerce environments, particularly for Gen Z users who value relational engagement.

Trust in platform influenced emotional trust but did not significantly affect cognitive trust. This suggests that general platform reputation may generate affective confidence but is insufficient for rational evaluations without direct experiential evidence such as interactivity or situational predictability.

Institutional assurance mechanisms including privacy policies, assurance seals and third-party certifications significantly influenced privacy concerns, with third-party certification having the strongest effect. Interestingly, these mechanisms appeared to heighten privacy awareness rather than reduce it. This finding aligns with the privacy

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salience effect, where visible security signals increase users' attention to potential risks. As a result, institutional mechanisms shape behavioural outcomes indirectly by influencing privacy perceptions.

Cognitive trust was found to significantly influence purchase intention, whereas emotional trust did not. This indicates that rational evaluations of platform reliability are the primary drivers of transactional behaviour among Gen Z users. Privacy concerns also significantly influenced purchase intention, and mediation analysis confirmed that institutional mechanisms affect purchase decisions through privacy perceptions.

Purchase intention strongly predicted customer satisfaction, which in turn significantly influenced repurchase intention. This sequential relationship confirms expectation-confirmation and loyalty theories suggesting that intention leads to satisfaction and subsequently to continued engagement. Further mediation analysis revealed that cognitive trust influences satisfaction through purchase intention, reinforcing its central role in driving long-term behavioural outcomes.

The study also identified several non-significant relationships that provide contextual insights. Familiarity did not contribute to trust formation, and situational normality did not influence emotional trust, suggesting that Gen Z users rely more on dynamic and interactive cues than static environmental familiarity. Similarly, general platform trust did not significantly affect cognitive trust, indicating that trust transfer is more nuanced and context dependent than previously assumed.

The findings offer important theoretical contributions by reinforcing the distinction between cognitive and emotional trust and demonstrating that these dimensions are shaped by different antecedents. The results extend trust transfer and institutional assurance theories by showing that security mechanisms may increase risk awareness rather than automatically reducing concerns. Moreover, the study highlights the dominant role of cognitive trust in shaping behavioural outcomes, supporting expectation-confirmation theory in digital commerce contexts.

From a practical perspective, the findings emphasize the importance of enhancing social interactivity as a key driver of trust. Platforms should prioritize responsive communication, user-generated feedback and social engagement features to foster both rational confidence and emotional comfort. Institutional mechanisms should be communicated transparently to avoid triggering unnecessary privacy anxiety. Additionally, maintaining consistent operational reliability is essential for converting trust into satisfaction and long-term loyalty.

The study recommends that social commerce platforms invest in interactive features, clear security communication and reliable transactional systems. Personalized engagement strategies may further strengthen both cognitive and emotional trust

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among Gen Z users.

Despite its contributions, the study has limitations. The cross-sectional design restricts causal interpretation, and the reliance on self-reported data may introduce bias. The focus on Gen Z Instagram users also limits generalizability. Future research could adopt longitudinal designs, include behavioural data and explore moderating variables such as risk perception or cultural factors.

References

- Agmeka, F., Wathoni, R. N., & Santoso, A. S. (2019). The influence of discount framing towards brand reputation and brand image on purchase intention and actual behaviour in e-commerce. *Procedia Computer Science*, 161, 851–858.
- Ajzen, I. (1991). The theory of planned behavior. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 50(2), 179–211.
- Alkhalifah, A. (2022). Exploring trust formation and antecedents in social commerce. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12, 789863.
- Alzaidi, M. S., & Agag, G. (2022). The role of trust and privacy concerns in using social media for e-retail services: The moderating role of COVID-19. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 68, 103042.
- Baer, M. D., van der Werff, L., Colquitt, J. A., Rodell, J. B., Zipay, K. P., & Buckley, F. (2018). Trusting the “look and feel”: Situational normality, situational aesthetics, and the perceived trustworthiness of organizations. *Academy of Management Journal*, 61(5), 1718–1740.
- Beatty, P., Reay, I., Dick, S., & Miller, J. (2011). *Consumer trust in e-commerce web sites: A meta-study*. *ACM Computing Surveys (CSUR)*, 43(3), 1–46.
- Belanger, F., Hiller, J. S., & Smith, W. J. (2002). Trustworthiness in electronic commerce: The role of privacy, security, and site attributes. *Journal of Strategic Information Systems*, 11(3–4), 245–270.
- Bryman, A., & Bell, E. (2015). *Business research methods (4th ed.)*. Oxford University Press.
- Chang, S. H., Chih, W. H., Liou, D. K., & Yang, Y. T. (2016). The mediation of cognitive attitude for online shopping. *Information Technology & People*, 29(3), 618–646.
- Chen, X., Wang, J., & Wei, S. (2022). The role of situational normality, swift guanxi, and perceived effectiveness of social commerce institutional mechanisms: An uncertainty reduction perspective. *Industrial Management & Data Systems*, 122(12), 2609–2632.

Journal of Management & Social Science
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Chin, W. W. (1998). The partial least squares approach to structural equation modeling. In G. A. Marcoulides (Ed.), *Modern methods for business research* (pp. 295–336). Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.

Chong, A. Y. L., Lacka, E., Li, B., & Chan, H. K. (2018). The role of social media in enhancing competitive advantage: An analysis of trust and interactivity. *Information & Management*, 55(5), 712–722.

Creswell, J. W. (2014). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods of approaches* (4th ed.). Sage Publications.

Eandhizhai, P. G. (2025). Gen Z consumer psychology on social media: The influence of eWOM and perceived value on purchase intention. *TPM Journal of Consumer Psychology*, 35(2), 112–129.

Etikan, I., Musa, S. A., & Alkassim, R. S. (2016). Comparison of convenience sampling and purposive sampling. *American Journal of Theoretical and Applied Statistics*, 5(1), 1–4.

Fang, Y., Qureshi, I., Sun, H., McCole, P., Ramsey, E., & Lim, K. H. (2014). Trust, satisfaction, and online repurchase intention. *MIS Quarterly*, 38(2), 407–427.

Festinger, L. (1957). *A theory of cognitive dissonance*. Stanford University Press.

Fornell, C., & Larcker, D. F. (1981). Evaluating structural equation models with unobservable variables and measurement error. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 18(1), 39–50

Foroutan, R. A., & Sarokolaei, M. G. (2022). *Online customer behavior: An analysis of the effects of cognitive and affective trust*. *Current Chinese Science*, 2(1), 45–56.

Gefen, D. (2000). E-commerce: The role of familiarity and trust. *Omega*, 28(6), 725–737.

Gefen, D., Karahanna, E., & Straub, D. W. (2003). Trust and TAM in online shopping: An integrated model. *MIS Quarterly*, 27(1), 51–90.

Gong, X., Zhang, K. Z. K., Chen, C., Cheung, C. M. K., & Lee, M. K. O. (2020). What drives trust transfer from web to mobile payment services? The dual effects of perceived entitativity. *Information & Management*, 57 (7), 103250.

Gunawan, A. I., Amalia, F. A., & Djatnika, T. (2022). Digital payment technology for SMEs: Can it be adopted and used properly? In *Proceedings of the 2022 International Conference on ICT for Smart Society (ICISS)* (pp. 1–6).

Gulati, R., & Sytch, M. (2008). Does familiarity breed trust? Revisiting the antecedents of trust. *Managerial and Decision Economics*, 29(2–3), 165–190.

Journal of Management & Social Science
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Hair, J. F., Hult, G. T. M., Ringle, C. M., & Sarstedt, M. (2017). A primer on partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS- SEM) (2nd ed.). Sage Publications.

Hair, J. F., Risher, J. J., Sarstedt, M., & Ringle, C. M. (2019). When to use and how to report the results of PLS- SEM. *European Business Review*, 31(1), 2–24.

Hajli, N. (2015). Social commerce constructs and consumer's intention to buy. *International Journal of Information Management*, 35(2), 183–191.

Hanabir, H. (2023). Factors impacting repurchase intentions in social commerce. *Marketing Expert Journal*, 11(4), 67–82.

Henseler, J., Ringle, C. M., & Sarstedt, M. (2015). A new criterion for assessing discriminant validity in variance-based structural equation modeling. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 43(1), 115–135.

Hoffman, D. L., Novak, T. P., & Peralta, M. (1999). Building consumer trust online. *Communications of the ACM*, 42(4), 80–85.

Hu, L. T., & Bentler, P. M. (1999). Cutoff criteria for fit indexes in covariance structure analysis: Conventional criteria versus new alternatives. *Structural Equation Modeling: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 6(1), 1–55.

Hu, X., Wu, G., & Wu, Y. (2010). Effects of perceived interactivity, perceived web assurance, and disposition to trust on initial online trust. *Journal of Computer- Mediated Communication*, 16(1), 1–26.

Joshi, A., Kale, S., Chandel, S., & Pal, D. K. (2015). Likert scale: Explored and explained. *British Journal of Applied Science & Technology*, 7(4), 396–403.

Kerkhof, P., & van Noort, G. (2010). Thirdparty Internet seals: Reviewing the effects on online consumer trust. In I. Lee (Ed.), *Encyclopedia of ebusiness development and management in the global economy* (pp. 701–708). IGI Global.

Kline, R. B. (2015). *Principles and practice of structural equation modeling* (4th ed.). Guilford Press.

Kim, D. J., Ferrin, D. L., & Rao, H. R. (2008). A trust-based consumer decision-making model in electronic commerce. *Decision Support Systems*, 44(2), 544–564.

Lakho, A., & Rashid, S. (2025). The trust factor: Influence of social media marketing on online purchase intentions of Generation Z in Pakistan. *Journal of Business and Management Research*, 4(1), 45–62.

Lăzăroiu, G., Neguriță, O., Grecu, I., & Grecu, G. (2020). *Consumers' decision-making*

Journal of Management & Social Science
VOL-3, ISSUE-1, 2026

process on social commerce platforms: Online trust, perceived risk, and purchase intentions. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 11, 890.

Lin, X., Wang, X., & Hajli, N. (2019). Building e-commerce satisfaction and boosting sales: The role of social commerce trust and its antecedents. *International Journal of Electronic Commerce*, 23(3), 328–363.

Liu, C., Marchewka, J. T., Lu, J., & Yu, C. S. (2018). Beyond concern: A privacy- trust- behavioral intention model of electronic commerce. *Information & Management*, 42(2), 289–304.

Lu, B., & Yi, X. (2023). Institutional trust and repurchase intention in the sharing economy: The moderating roles of information privacy concerns and security concerns. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 70, 103–118.

Malhotra, N. K., Kim, S. S., & Agarwal, J. (2004). Internet users' information privacy concerns (IUIPC): The construct, the scale, and a causal model. *Information Systems Research*, 15(4), 336–355.

McKnight, D. H., Choudhury, V., & Kacmar, C. (2002). Developing and validating trust measures for e-commerce: An integrative typology. *Information Systems Research*, 13(3), 334–359.

Miao, M., Jalees, T., Zaman, S. I., & Khan, S. (2022). *The influence of e-customer satisfaction, e-trust and perceived value on consumer's repurchase intention in B2C e-commerce segment*. *Asia Pacific Journal of Marketing and Logistics*, 34(5), 1032–1050.

Mousavizadeh, S. M. (2016). *Three research essays on online users' concerns and web assurance mechanisms* (Doctoral dissertation, University of North Texas). ProQuest Dissertations Publishing.

Mubdir, G. A., Hashim, S., Ayob, A., & Rosli, N. (2025). Customer engagement and social commerce trends: A systematic review. *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, 15(1), 9452.

Nabi, F., Yong, J. M., Tao, X., Malhi, M. S., Farhan, M., & Mahmood, U. (2021). Process of security assurance technique for application functional logic in e-commerce systems. *Journal of Information Security*, 12(3), 189–211.

National Commission for the Protection of Human Subjects of Biomedical and Behavioral Research. (1979). *The Belmont Report: Ethical principles and guidelines for the protection of human subjects of research*. U.S. Government Printing Office.

Nieves-Pavón, S., & Sánchez González, M. J. (2025). *Social and cognitive factors influencing trust and purchase intention in organic e-commerce: A gender-based analysis*. *Sustainability*,

Journal of Management & Social Science
VOL-3, ISSUE-1, 2026

17(3), 456.

Oliver, R. L. (1980). A cognitive model of the antecedents and consequences of satisfaction decisions. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 17(4), 460–469.

Oliver, R. L. (1999). Whence consumer loyalty? *Journal of Marketing*, 63(Special Issue), 33–44.

Oliveira, T., Alinho, M., Rita, P., & Dhillon, G. (2017). Modelling and testing consumer trust dimensions in e-commerce. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 71, 153–164.

Oesterreich, T. D., Anton, E., Hettler, F. M., & Teuteberg, F. (2025). What drives individuals' trusting intention in digital platforms? A meta-analysis. *Management Review Quarterly*, 75(4), 3615–3667.

Ou, C. X., Pavlou, P. A., & Davison, R. M. (2014). Swift trust in online marketplaces: The role of social interactivity. *Decision Support Systems*, 57, 210–220.

Özpolat, K., Gao, G. (., Jank, W., & Viswanathan, S. (2013). Research note—the value of third-party assurance seals in online retailing: An empirical investigation. *Information Systems Research*, 24(4), 1100–1111.

Park, I., Bhatnagar, A., & Rao, H. R. (2010). *Assurance seals, online customer satisfaction, and repurchase intention*. *International Journal of Electronic Commerce*, 14(3), 11–34.

Pappas, I. O., Giannakos, M. N., & Kourouthanassis, P. E. (2013). *Assessing emotions related to privacy and trust in personalized services*. *Proceedings of the International Conference on e-Business*, 1–10.

Pavlou, P. A. (2003). Consumer acceptance of electronic commerce: Integrating trust and risk with the Technology Acceptance Model. *International Journal of Electronic Commerce*, 7(3), 101–134.

Pavlou, P. A., & Gefen, D. (2004). Building effective online marketplaces with institution-based trust. *Information Systems Research*, 15(1), 37–59.

Peterson, D., Meinert, D., Criswell, J., & Crossland, M. (2007). Consumer trust: Privacy policies and third-party seals. *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*, 14(4), 654–669.

Podsakoff, P. M., MacKenzie, S. B., Lee, J. Y., & Podsakoff, N. P. (2003). Common method biases in behavioral research: A critical review. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 88(5), 879–903.

Ponte, E., Carvajal-Trujillo, E., & Escobar-Rodríguez, T. (2015). Influence of trust and

Journal of Management & Social Science
VOL-3, ISSUE-1, 2026

perceived value on the intention to purchase travel online: Integrating the effects of assurance on trust antecedents. *Tourism Management*, 47, 286–302.

Podsakoff, P. M., MacKenzie, S. B., Lee, J. Y., & Podsakoff, N. P. (2003). Common method biases in behavioral research: A critical review. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 88(5), 879–903.

Punyatoya, P. (2019). Effects of cognitive and affective trust on online customer satisfaction and loyalty. *Journal of Business Research*, 104, 183–195.

Putri, N. A. (2023). *The effect of privacy concern on repurchase intention: E-trust and e-satisfaction as mediators in online shopping*. *ITB Journal of Business and Economics*, 12(2), 45–63.

Putri, N., Prasetya, Y., Handayani, P. W., & Fitriani, H. (2024). TikTok Shop: How trust and privacy influence Generation Z's purchasing behaviors. *Cogent Social Sciences*, 10(1), 2292759. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311886.2023.2292759> (doi.org in Bing)

Ray, S., Ow, T., & Kim, S. S. (2011). Security assurance: How online service providers can influence security control perceptions and gain trust. *Decision Sciences*, 42(2), 391–412.

Rousseau, D. M., Sitkin, S. B., Burt, R. S., & Camerer, C. (1998). Not so different after all: A crossdiscipline view of trust. *Academy of Management Review*, 23(3), 393–404.

Saffanah, L., Handayani, P. W., & Sunarso, F. P. (2023). Actual purchases on Instagram live shopping: The influence of live shopping engagement and information technology affordance. *Asia Pacific Management Review*, 28(2), 204–214.

Senali, M. G., Iranmanesh, M., Ghobakhloo, M., Foroughi, B., Asadi, S., & Rejeb, A. (2024). Determinants of trust and purchase intention in social commerce. *Electronic Commerce Research and Applications*, 61, 101286.

Shahid, S., & Ikram, A. (2024). *Navigating the digital landscape: Impact of Instagram influencers' credibility on consumer behaviour among Gen Z and Millennials*. *Pakistan Journal of Social Sciences*, 41(2), 112–128.

Soeharso, S. Y. (2024). Customer satisfaction as a mediator between service quality to repurchase intention in online shopping. *Cogent Business & Management*, 11(1), Article 2336304.

Sohaib, O., & Kang, K. (2016). Individual level culture effects on trust in B2C e-commerce. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 56, 174–185.

Singh, R. (2022). “Hey Alexa—order groceries for me”: The effect of consumerVAI emotional attachment on satisfaction and repurchase intention. *European Journal of*

Journal of Management & Social Science
VOL-3, ISSUE-1, 2026

Marketing, 56(13), 1–23.

Stewart, K. J. (2003). Trust transfer on the World Wide Web. *Organization Science*, 14(1), 5–17.

Szymkowiak, A., Melović, B., Dabić, M., Jeganathan, K., & Kundi, G. S. (2021). Information technology and Gen Z: The role of trust in social commerce. *Journal of Business Research*, 137, 1–12.

Trivedi, S. K., & Yadav, M. (2020). Repurchase intentions in Generation Y: Mediation of trust and e satisfaction. *Marketing Intelligence & Planning*, 38(4), 401–415.

Tseng, H., Jia, S., Nisar, T. M., Hajli, N., & Shabbir, H. (2025). The study of social commerce in Generation Z context: The role of social support and privacy risk. *Information Technology & People*, 38(3), 1505–1525.

Wang, J., Shahzad, F., Ahmad, Z., Abdullah, M. A., & Hassan, M. (2022). Trust and consumers' purchase intention in social commerce: A meta-analytic approach. *SAGE Open*, 12(1), 1–16.

Wang, H., Meng, Y., & Wang, W. (2013). The role of perceived interactivity in virtual communities: Building trust and increasing stickiness. *Connection Science*, 25(1), 55–73.

Wang, M. Y., Zhang, P. Z., Zhou, C. Y., & Lai, N. Y. (2019). Effect of emotion, expectation, and privacy on purchase intention in WeChat health product consumption: The mediating role of trust. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 16(20), 3861.

Wang, Y., Lin, X., Zhang, H., & Macias, W. (2022). Establishing consumer trust in social commerce: Cognitive and affective appraisal. *Electronic Commerce Research and Applications*, 53, 101–118.

Wiyata, W. (2023). Customers' trust transferability in social commerce and its impact on perceived risk and purchase intention. *International Journal of Social Sciences Research*, 4(2), 78–101.

Wu, G., Hu, X., & Wu, Y. (2010). Effects of perceived interactivity, perceived web assurance, and disposition to trust on initial online trust. *Journal of Computer Mediated Communication*, 16(1), 1–26.

Wu, W., Wang, S., Ding, G., & Mo, J. (2023). Elucidating trust-building sources in social shopping: A consumer cognitive and emotional trust perspective. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 71, 103217.

Yousafzai, S. Y., Pallister, J. G., & Foxall, G. R. (2003). A proposed model of etrust for

Journal of Management & Social Science
VOL-3, ISSUE-1, 2026

electronic banking. *Tech novation*, 23(11), 847–860.

Zhao, L., & Lu, Y. (2012). Enhancing perceived interactivity through network externalities: An empirical study on micro-blogging service satisfaction and continuance intention. *Decision Support Systems*, 53(4), 825–834.